

Coffee & Hereditary Hair Loss

„Alopecia Androgenetica“

New study and new insight

Current theories are questioned

The end of the era Hereditary Hair Loss

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Abstract

Background: Study of the historical information and finds showed few presents of today's bald head „AGA“. The deeper we look in the past the less it appears to be present.

We've noticed a link between the historic coffee spread and the baldness spread. Countries in east asia have been showing increasing in the baldness prevalence since coffee imports.

Methods: We conducted a two stage study. In the first stage we conducted a survey on 1466 People. We divided them in two groups, with and without relevant bald areas.

In the second stage we conducted an experimental study on 320 experimentees with hair loss and bald areas. Thus we divided them in 4 groups and tested the coffee effect with and without exposure.

Results: A significant common denominator among the people with relevant bald areas in the survey at stage 1 was exposure to coffee.

In stage 2 groups protected from coffee exposure including protection from volatile coffee compounds shows a significant new hair growth and a significant decline of the bald areas and completely stop of the hair loss.

Conclusions: The hair loss according to Norwood-Hamilton pattern occurs on the effect of coffee or coffee compounds in the first line.

Introduction

The baldness according to Norwood-Hamilton pattern „AGA“ is a plague of humanity since many centuries. It hits millions of people in an upward trend, doctors, poets, thinkers, popes, kings, presidents and well-known personalities. And the cause is not finally clarified. There are too much assumptions and superstitions. Currently, in some region, Turkey as example the rate of bald heads there reaches over 67.1% of men in average and reaches over 90% in men over 70 years old¹. In India the rate of bald heads reaches 58% of men under 50 years old², and the prevalence increases with age. According to Hamilton's study in 1951 the prevalence of AGA reaches approximately 50% in men at the age of 50. Recently according to the American Hair Loss Association by the age of 50 approximately 85% of men will have significant hair thinning. The observation in the last decades shows even an increase in regions traditionally known for high rates of balding. Other regions with so far lower rates are currently showing rising rates, following this trend³. The research shows that the trend of balding had its origin around and after the 12th century, mainly in the mediterranean area. However, it began to expand between the 15th and 16th century and later became an omnipresent problem. We can observe this happening by increased mention in the literature as well as sculptures originating from this time, but also the newly created wigs culture of the 17 century. The old history shows that this phenomenon in its current known form was not a trendy or less present. As we have seen it through sculptures and finds of earlier times, particularly in sculptures and finds of Mesopotamia and Ancient Egypt, but even in the original Roman and Greek finds unlike some copies after the 14th century. The clear trend was to see a full head of hair until old age and even without relevant receding hairline.

Now, what has changed in the last few centuries? What came new in the world? Has the genetics of humans changed or was the Dihydrotestosterone "DHT" what is the body's own at one time on certain hair follicles without the others incompatible?

Much more coffee is the new thing in the world, it's the new healer. We noticed that the coffee culture and baldness spread at the same time around 12th to 16th century and conquered the entire Mediterranean area. In the same context, until yet this region shows so far the highest values of baldness in the world.

At the same period of time, the Kippah has spread among Jews, the Taqiyah among Muslims and the Zucchetto among Christians. And so this became after that the culture of each group. Later in the 17th century we saw the wig among the Europeans⁷⁻¹¹.

The historical research shows the same common course of coffee spreading and the well-known rituals of hiding the bald spot.

The evolution of the examined values over the time line, in percent for the respective groups

Chart 1: Shows the relation between coffee spreading and baldness or the means against over the time line
Data according to the references⁴⁻¹¹

The baldness phenomenon became later so firmly anchored in people's consciousness that they saw it as a natural phenomenon. They probably thought this had been every time like that, and it appeared repeatedly in the history books and works like something very normal. To date, scientists are searching in genetics for guilty, but without success.

This is not the only aspect that we observed, the evidence has increased enormously that we would have to scientifically check whether coffee has an effect on balding or not. See additional information and discussion.

Study

We conducted a two stage study. In the first stage, we asked 1466 male subjects between the ages of 22 and 45 about their lifestyle and circumstances, and we asked particularly three questions as shown below. Among those were 716 persons with clearly visible bald areas and 750 persons with no relevant bald areas. In the second stage we performed an experiment with 320 subjects.

People with alopecia areata, a. universalis or patients under the influence of chemotherapy were excluded. Because we wanted to investigate exactly the cause of hereditary hair loss and not the other forms of hair loss. So the patient must have a bald head that can be classified according to the Norwood-Hamilton pattern and the hair loss must be in the crown area.

Methods

Stage 1

1466 people were interviewed and divided into two groups. First group counts 716 people who had bald areas. The second group counts 750 people without relevant bald areas.

Both groups 1&2 were asked the same questions as follows:

- 1- Do you drink coffee daily or are you exposed to coffee flavor every day?
- 2- Do you occasionally drink coffee or are you occasionally exposed to coffee flavor?
- 3- Do you rarely drink coffee or are you rarely exposed to coffee flavor?

Respondents could answer these 3 questions with yes or no.

Stage 2

320 male subjects with hair loss problems participated in the experiment, they were between the ages of 19 and 40. They were selected according to their degree of baldness and divided into two main groups. The first group included persons with visible bald areas, there were 280 subjects. The second group included persons with hair loss without visible bald areas, there were 40 subjects between the ages of 19 and 27 years.

First group was divided into two subgroups of 140 persons each, group 1 A and group 1 B.

Group 1 A was asked to give up coffee completely, but also coffee flavor should be avoided.

Group 1 B was asked to eat healthily but continue to drink coffee as usual.

Second group was divided into two subgroups of 20 people each. Group 2 A and Group 2 B.

Group 2 A was asked to give up coffee completely, but also coffee flavor should be avoided.

Group 2 B was asked to drink more coffee. At least 3 cups spread throughout the day.

We did monthly image checks. And each time we asked the participants how they felt about it and how they kept to the commandment.

Outcomes

Stage 1

From **group 1** „people with bald areas“ have **620** people answered the question - Do you drink coffee daily or are you exposed to coffee flavor daily? - with yes. From **group 2** „people without relevant bald areas“ have **80** people answered the same question with yes.

To the second question - Do you occasionally drink coffee or are you occasionally exposed to coffee flavor? - answered **90** from **group 1** with yes and **300** from **group 2** with yes.

To the third question - Do you rarely drink coffee or are you rarely exposed to coffee flavor? - answered only **6** from **group 1** with yes and **370** from **group 2** with yes.

In chart 2 & 3, the relation between coffee exposure and baldness is clearly visible in the 1466 people survey.

Chart 2: Shows that the most bald people have a coffee exposure, in 87% daily and in 12% occasionally.

Chart 3: Shows that people without bald areas in average have less coffee exposure than people with bald areas.

Stage 2

21 subjects in **group 1 A "which was asked to keep away from coffee"** have abandoned the attempt. 119 continued with for at least 3 months. In 108 subjects, we could see new hair growth and a decline of bald areas after 3 months at the latest. In subjects with hair loss, this has completely stopped within the first month. 10 subjects showed stable conditions. The younger the subject was the stronger the decline of baldness. Another part of the subjects we could track over a longer period than 3 months. We found a period of 6 months is better to document a clear difference for before and after.

11 subjects in **group 1 B "which was asked to continue with coffee as usual"** have abandoned the attempt. The experiment continued with 129 subjects. After 3 months, 69 subjects showed worsening. 59 subjects showed stable conditions. No relevant improvement was recorded.

3 subjects in **group 2 A "which was asked to keep away from coffee"** have canceled the experiment. 17 subjects participated in the experiment for 8 weeks. In 16 subjects hair loss has stopped completely.

4 subjects in **group 2 B "which was asked to drink more coffee"** have canceled the experiment. 16 subjects participated for 8 weeks. In 14 subjects, we could see a significant deterioration. 2 subjects showed stable conditions. No improvement was noted.

The 40 subjects in group 2 were individuals who showed initial hair loss, thus showing sensitivity to coffee. This has increased with the increase in coffee quantity and have improved a lot when they leave it out.

In chart 4 the coffee effect on progression of baldness or decline can be seen very well.

Chart 4: Shows coffee effect on all groups

Case example

After 4 months

Initial

Our assessment shows that people show a different sensitivity to coffee compounds, where the hereditary component plays a role „sensitivity to coffee compounds“. Tissue anatomy and metabolism vary depending on the genetic. Approximately 40% of men react to coffee compounds with hair loss and baldness within 1-10 years. Another 40% react delayed and get a visible bald head after 10 to 30 years or more. The remaining 20% are not sensitive or less sensitive. And here's the difficulty, why no one could find the cause of hair loss until now. It is up to the 20% who are not sensitive. They have camouflaged this effect.

We can summarize the following: Not every coffee drinker is bald but almost every bald head according to Norwood-Hamilton pattern is exposed in a way to coffee compounds.

Conclusions:

The hair loss according to Norwood-Hamilton pattern occurs on the effect of coffee or coffee compounds in the first line. Hereditary is only the degree of sensitivity of individuals on coffee compounds. Some individuals respond in very short time to very small amounts and some take much longer time and need larger amounts.

Abbreviations:

AGA: Alopecia androgenetica

ANH: Alopecia according to Norwood-Hamilton

Acknowledgment: I confirm that I have not received any funds from any side. I have been following and completing this work myself.

Additional information and discussion:

Currently the coffee effect can be observed clearly on tea cultures in east asia as they since decades gradually evolve into coffee cultures. Japan and South Korea but also China are good examples. They have been showing lower levels of bald heads than the Mediterranean and European until recently, but they have been catching up lately.

A chart example of Japan. Here it is clear to see the relation between increasing coffee consumption and increasing number of bald people. Similar increase in both values in many asian countries.

Chart 5: Shows the relation between coffee consumption and the prevalence of baldness in the case of Japan
Data according to All Japan Coffee Association & a survey conducted by Aderans Co.Ltd Japan

We can also observe the same developments in South Korea. Since the beginning of the 20th century, South Korea has gradually developed into coffee culture, while the last 30 years have been the culmination of this development¹²⁻¹⁴. To notice is too, that in 20 years trend between 1990-2010 the number of the AGA under the alopecia patient is nearly doubled from 38.9% to 76.7%^{3&15}.

The next chart shows the relation between coffee consumption and AGA prevalence among alopecia patients between 1990-2010. This also indicate an increase in the general AGA prevalence among the korean population.

Chart 6: Shows the relation between the increase of coffee consumption and the increase of AGA among alopecia patients Data according to the international coffee organization (ico) and Chung-Ang University hospital in Seoul.

If we compare the data from the Chung-Ang University Hospital in Seoul between 1990 to 1993 and 2007 to 2010. Then we would see a significant progression in baldness among Koreans. Within 4 years between the years 1990-1993, 286 male patients with AGA visited "The Department of Dermatology" at Chung-Ang University Hospital. In the same 4 years period 17 years later between 2007 and 2010, 701 male patients with AGA visited the same hospital for treatment. So we have an increase in incidence of 145% within 17 years. So we estimate that the prevalence of AGA among Korean men 1990 and before would have to be around 10% or below. 2010 the prevalence of AGA reaches over 20% and the trend is increasing so that we expect it will reach over 30% in the next survey if the coffee trend continues. The age of AGA onset is also gradually decreased from 34.1 ± 10.1 years 2006 to 31.6 ± 10.9 years 2010³.

Between 1997-1999, the prevalence of baldness among Korean men was 14.1%, thus about 6.4 million Korean men until 2000 were affected¹⁶, in 2010 this number increased to about 10 million men with a prevalence increases to about 20-22% and the number is constantly increasing^{17&18}.

Interestingly, similar consumption of coffee quantity in Japan and South Korea shows closer "AGA" prevalence numbers.

With consumption of 1.7 kg of coffee per capita in the years 1982/83 in Japan, the AGA prevalence there was 15.6% and with consumption of 1.4 kg of coffee per capita in the year 1999 in South Korea, the AGA prevalence was 14.1% there. The numbers have continued to rise and the prevalence is rising and getting closer and closer.

This comparison shows how similar coffee quantity show similar baldness prevalence compared Japan to South Korea.

Chart 7: Compare the coffee quantity and the baldness prevalence in comparison between Japan and South Korea According to the data above

This shows also a 2% increased sensitivity to coffee of the Koreans as the Japanese, otherwise it is only due to the accuracy of the data. Calculated as follows: $1.4 / (1.4 + 1.7) \times 100 = 45\%$ this number meets 47% baldness prevalence equivalent, it shows increase in 2%.

The global trade statistics for the next few years also show clearly the relation between the two values

Chart 8: Shows the relation between the global coffee market and the global alopecia market for the next few years Data according to Mordor Intelligence & Inkwoodresearch^{19&20}

The current flood of studies on the very healthy effect of coffee „caffeine“ is encouraging more and more people to become coffee drinkers and this boosts the hair loss effect very clearly.

Could coffee be that harmful? let us make a look deeper into the coffee compounds.

Coffee under the magnifying glass.

Coffee does not just contain caffeine, we think further than just looking at studies on caffeine. Dissolved active substances as well as volatile active substances are in our focus.

The coffee aroma contains many bioactive compounds, there are far more than 1000 compounds. In the picture below is a result of an analysis of the coffee aroma with the Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry "GC-MS". Here you could see the immense density of chemical compounds. Among them are proven harmful compounds.

Picture 2: GC-MS analysis of coffee compounds

To read the GC-MS analysis, proceed as shown in Picture 3.

Picture 3: It shows how to proceed with the GC-MS analysis

We take only two compounds as an example of the harmful effect.

Carbon disulfide:

Carbon disulfide is good fat-soluble, it is easily absorbed through the lungs and skin. Prolonged exposure leads to symptoms of intoxication:

Coronary heart disease, retinal angiopathy, color discrimination, effects on peripheral nerves, psychophysiological effects, morphological and other central nervous system (CNS) effects, and fertility and hormonal effects. Decreased libido and or impotence among males occupationally exposed to high concentrations of carbon disulfide.

Menstrual disorders are more frequent than in the case of the healthy women, the average menopausal age is statistically earlier, and complex disturbances in neurohormonal system including diminished secretion of estrogens and progesterone in ovaries and dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate in the adrenal gland.

DNA damage in human buccal cells of workers occupationally long-term exposed to carbon disulfide was monitored with comet assay, and the possibility of DNA damage was significantly higher in exposure group than that in control group. In human sperm exposed to carbon disulfide in vitro, there was a significant increase in the frequency of chromosomal aberrations and in the frequency of chromosomal breaks. DNA damage in mice sperm was detected. In experimental animals, carbon disulfide is embryotoxic and fetotoxic at high concentrations and is teratogenic at exposure levels toxic to the dam. Reduced hatching and developmental effects, particularly notochord deformities, were observed in the frog *Microhyla ornata* exposed to carbon disulfide.

Neurological effects such as hind-limb motor difficulties, reduced nerve conduction velocity, and degeneration of nerve fibers were seen in rats exposed to 700 ppm of carbon disulfide for 5 hours a day, 5 days a week, for 12 weeks. Other behavioral effects in rats included decreased responsiveness to a visual stimulus and mild tremors, reactivity in response to handling was increased, and excitability in the open field was decreased.²⁴⁻²⁵

Cresol:

Cresols is good fat-soluble, it is easily absorbed through the lungs and skin. Cresol can be perceived as odorous even in concentrations of a few micrograms per cubic meter of air. Contaminated open mucous membranes (oral cavity, nose, anus) they go directly into the blood, where they are rapidly distributed in the body and lead to multiple protein damage to the internal organs.

Poisoning causes quite unspecific symptoms. Signs of chronic poisoning include headache, cough and nausea, loss of appetite, and dullness and insomnia. Acute poisoning with kidney damage and central nervous system disorders such as seizures, unconsciousness and respiratory paralysis can be the result. Cresols are considered carcinogenic.

Phenols and especially cresols have a strong protein decomposition. Because they are highly corrosive, they cause acute skin damage on contact with the skin, destroy the protein of the skin cells and overcome the protective mechanism of the skin, which is slightly acidic, almost immediately.

In mice exposed to a mixture of o-cresol aerosol and vapor 2 hr/day, 6 days/week for 1 month no mortality was recorded. Clinical signs of toxicity during the daily exposure periods were limited to signs of respiratory

irritation at the start of the exposure, followed by a period of hypoactivity lasting until the end of the exposure. Microscopic examination revealed signs of irritation in the respiratory tract. Other lesions included degeneration of heart muscle, liver, kidney and nerve cells and glial elements of the central nervous system.

Hair depigmentation and microscopic effects on hair and skin biopsies. Repeats rough coat in experimental animals.

Without immediate initiation of countermeasures, cresols can have a life-threatening effect even in small quantities.²⁶⁻²⁷

Discussion:

As we have shown above, coffee is the cause of the development and spreading of hair loss and baldness ANH. Other hair loss forms such as alopecia areata were not considered here.

How does the coffee effect come about and why does it mainly affect the crown?

Possibly, in the coffee or in the coffee aroma volatile compounds with a light density accumulate there at the highest point and remain trapped in a way and trigger an inflammatory reaction or a tissue-damaging effect.

Why are women less affected than men and why do women show a different reaction pattern than men?

Men and women have different physiology and different types of hair and fat.

Possible reasons could be e.g. on physiology, tissue anatomy or the different reparative mechanisms of the two sexes.

The reparative mechanisms in women and young people could be more effective than those of adult men. Possibly in females the female hormone could play an effect.

Women's tissue anatomy could possibly tolerate more damage than the male.

The physiological status of the man could potentially trigger stronger or aggressive repair attempts, resulting in repeated reactions to tissue damage. Possibly male hormone could have an effect here.

Or there are predominantly in women but also in some men a metabolic situation which makes coffee effect more compatible. Or all the above factors play complementary roles for each other.

The theory of the determined genetics, which says hair loss ANH is a genetically determined phenomenon, would need to be reformed. And also the theory of the androgens need to be reformed as well.

Here we show a summary in picture series, which makes the topic easier to understand.

Determined genetics occurs without trigger, it begins at birth, or begins directly and could progress as the process progresses. A phenomenon that occurs in average after at least 18 years and which must first be triggered is not a determined genetics. However, there would be genetic susceptibility if the trigger factor affects it, so the phenomenon then becomes visible.

To accuse the DHT as a trigger factor is not tenable for many reasons.

For example, DHT is present in abundant concentration in the organism before the age of 18, and continuously decreases after the age of 40. But the hair loss usually does not occur before the age of 18, and in many people the baldness develops after the age of 40 years. Respectively for what reasons should the hair follicles not tolerate the DHT at once? And why only the hair follicles in the crown and not the remaining hair follicles?

Our recommendation:

It is important to formulate a new definition for the above-discussed hair loss form, where it is now quite clear that the term hereditary or hormone-induced hair loss is no longer appropriate.

We recommend treating coffee the same way as smoking. Excluding coffee from workplaces and confined spaces would put an end to baldness at early age.

The therapy of young people with hair loss according to Hamilton-Norwood Pattern is the complete protection from coffee and coffee compounds especially in the coffee aromas. At latest after 3 months, the first signs of improvement should be noticeable.

We appeal to the decision-maker to check whether coffee is really suitable for human consumption. Because we found a link to certain diseases during our work. Such as hypertension, heart arrhythmia, bowel disease, hemorrhoid, memory and impaired concentration, hand tremors, increased sweating and seborrheic dermatitis.

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